

Appendix A: Supplemental Material

This appendix provides supplemental material for the paper “Using Process Mining with Pre- and Post-Intervention Analysis to Improve Digital Service Delivery: A Governmental Case Study”.

A.1 Personnel Security Screening Process

The Government of Canada processes tens of thousands of Personnel Security Screening (PSS) transactions per year. As a condition of employment, public servants working for the GC must undergo a security screening process. This rule also applies to contractors and third parties working with the GC.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, a GC department implemented a new PSS system, including an online web-based portal for new/prospective employees to complete their security screening application. The goals of this platform were to 1) improve processing times, for instance, by reducing data validation errors; and 2) facilitate a more contactless experience due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This new system was a highly suitable candidate for PM as it was built on an industry-recognized, low-code Business Process Management (BPM) platform. As a Process-Aware Information System (PAIS), the platform records key events throughout a case’s lifecycle at an adequate level of abstraction. Below, we summarize the PSS, its high-level process, and how the PSS system fits in.

Fig. 1: Personnel Security Screening (PSS) normative process overview

Different security levels exist, starting from *reliability status* and ending with *secret* and *top-secret* clearances. The security level required for an employee is determined by the sensitivity of information they will handle in their day-to-day work. During the tenure of a typical public servant, one can expect to change roles multiple times, and as such, they may need to upgrade their security clearance level. For a new public servant, assuming there are no adverse indicators in their PSS application, the high-level process for PSS is shown in Fig. 1.

After a security screening is requested by the hiring manager, the prospective employee fills out a standard application form. We note that, before the online

PSS portal was introduced, this form was typically submitted in PDF format via email to a departmental security office. Some applicants even opted to print the form, complete it by hand, and send it via regular mail. Both approaches to form submission were error prone; in practice, they often led to multiple re-submissions until all errors were resolved. This led to significant processing (and thus hiring) delays. After the introduction of the online PSS system, applicants could amend their application based on errors detected by the system before submission, i.e., without having to resubmit or (e-)mail an entirely new copy.

Once the application form is accepted for processing, the necessary reference checks and background verifications take place. If no adverse indicators are found, the individual is cleared to work for the GC. Finally, before employment begins for a new employee, a security briefing takes place, which explains employees' responsibilities as public servants when handling sensitive information. For the department we examined, security briefings were conducted one-on-one with the hiring manager.

A.2 Jupyter Notebook and Event Log

As a companion to this case study, we have shared a sample Jupyter notebook, as well as a synthetic event log, to illustrate the use of our `logprep4pm` library. The following GitHub repository includes everything needed to start using this library, along with documentation of the functions and their associated outputs: <https://github.com/ProcessMining-uOttawa/logprep4pm>*

* For confidentiality reasons, the artifacts provided are not from this case study, but still illustrate the general methodology that was used with a synthetic dataset.